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Research Article

A TO COMPARE THE EFFICIENCY OF VARIOUS ANTI-HYPERTENSION MEDICINESDr. Rimsha Masoud¹, Dr. Syed Rehan Hayder Naqvi², Dr. Abdul Khaliq³¹ Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore² Civil Medical Officer BHU Halan Shamali Tehsil & District Haveli, AJK³ Medical Officer at BHU 23/MB District Khushab**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of our study was to find out the efficiency of various types of medicines used for hypertensive curing.

Design of Study: Observation based comparison study.

Duration and Place: Medicine department of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from January, 2020 to March 2020 for the duration of 60 days.

Materials and methods: The time duration of the study was 3 months. We selected a total number of 300 patients of hypertension for the study. Four groups were formulated, Each group consisting of 75 patients. The Medicines of four types given to each group include atenolol, captopril, amlodipine and irbesartan. After the time interval of 15 days, 30 days, and 60 days, checked and noted the blood pressure of all patients.

Results: According to the observations pressure of the blood noticed as reduced in all groups. Compared to other drugs irbesartan showed very good result in reducing the blood pressure.

Conclusion: Compared to other medicines of hypertension, irbesartan is much more affective for taking control of blood pressure as per findings of current observational study. But for more good description of antihypertensive drugs, much more research is needed.

Key words: Captopril, Atenolol, Irbesartan, Antihypertensive Drugs, Amlodipine.

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INTRODUCTION:

Rise in Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure levels, increases the hazard of coronary atherosclerotic disease. With a rise in systolic blood pressure levels diastolic blood pressure levels, hazard of coronary atherosclerotic disease is directly in relation. According to study by Frohlich et al in 2010, with old age, occurrence of left ventricular hypertrophy rises and in hypertensive patients this rate is higher. Power of the blood experienced on any unitary vessel wall area is known as Blood Pressure levels. Guyton et al describes in his study in 2013 that diastolic/systolic pressure, peripheral vascular resistance, cardiac output and maximum pressure in arteries are the factors of systolic blood pressure. Complications can be well indicated by systolic blood pressure as per findings of Massie in 2014. Increased death and illness were greatly considered as by the reason of increase in the systolic and diastolic blood pressure for very long duration in the persons having age more than 50 years.

Incessant blood pressure in males and females was reported in many epidemiological researches on ethnic groups, old age persons, middle and young aged people in the country by Vasani et al in 2013. With diastolic blood pressure variation, risk of disease increases as observed in a study on 100 adult persons as illness is in relation with the abnormal high BP with sufficient rise. According to the findings of Chobanian et al in 2012, hypertensive condition will be considered when diastolic BP is more than 95mmHg and systolic BP is more than 160mmHg. Hypertension is usually developed through lazy life styles and by many physical exercises blood pressure can be maintained at normal level. Schiffrin et al in 2009 described the related factors as endothelial dysfunction and genetic dysfunction. Vikrant in his study in 2010 also stated that functional vasoconstriction or structural thickening might be a factor.

Pastor Barriuso et al in 2013 in his epidemiological study reported an absolute dividing line among normal blood pressure and abnormal blood pressure. According to Frohlich et al (2012) patients of hypertension have a direct risk of cardiovascular complications, as hypertension also known as heterogeneous disorder and it can be controlled by adopting different pathophysiological methods. Essential hypertension is also a type of hypertension in which specific medical condition of patient can

not be explained. Carretero stated in his study in 2000 that about 90 percent to 95 percent cases of hypertension are having essential hypertension.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was carried out in the Medicine department of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from January, 2020 to March 2020 for the duration of 60 days. Selected a total number of 300 patients of hypertension for the study after a diet regimen i.e controlling sodium in regular diet, exercise for half an hour/day and everyday physical activity with alteration in food, change of lifestyle for 30 days interval and weight loss. Consisting of 75 patients each, formed four groups. Medicine of four types given to each group include atenolol, captopril, amlodipine and irbesartan.

Essential hypertension was newly diagnosed in all selected patients and age of both genders was in the range of 25 years to 75 years. Carried out modifications in lifestyle of the patients during present study, for minimum of 01 month with controlled BP. Established the mean reading of blood pressure by recording it 3 times daily. Excludability criteria was as patients already taking antihypertensive drugs, liver dysfunction and asthma, breastfeeding mothers, pregnant women, patients with history of unstable angina or coronary artery disease, NSAIDs and antihypertensives allergy test groups.

RESULTS:

On first day and 30th day patients treated with amlodipine showed mean $\pm$ SEM Systolic BP values as 154.2 ± 1.62 mmHg and 152.0 ± 1.94 mmHg respectively and 143.8 ± 1.98 mmHg after 60 days with decrease of 4.7 %. Patients treated with atenolol on first day, 30th day and 60th day showed systolic mean values as 157.8 ± 2.72 mmHg, 146.6 ± 2.91 mmHg and 137.2 ± 2.40 mmHg respectively with decrease of 8.6%. Patients treated with captopril on first day, 30th day and 60th day showed systolic mean values as 157.3 ± 2.43 mmHg, 148.6 ± 2.51 mmHg and 139.8 ± 2.98 mmHg respectively with decrease of 7.7%. Patients treated with Irbesartan on first day, 30th day and 60th day showed systolic mean values as 160.2 ± 1.97 mmHg, 145.8 ± 1.80 mmHg and 131.4 ± 2.28 mmHg respectively with decrease of 13.4%. results are shown below in table No 01.

Table No 01: Changes in mean systolic Bp from 1st day to day 60

Groups (n=75)	Day 1 st (mmHg)	Day 30 (mmHg)	Day 60 (mmHg)	Decrease % Day 1 st -60
Amlodipine	154.2±1.62	152.0±1.94	143.8±1.98	4.70
Atenolol	157.8±2.72	146.6±2.91	137.2±2.40	8.60
Captopril	157.3±2.43	148.6±2.51	139.8±2.98	7.70
Irbesartan	160.2±1.97	145.8±1.80	131.4±2.28	13.4

Mean±SEM: P<0.01 significantly decreases from 1st day

P<0.01 significantly decreases from day 1st and day 30

Patients treated with amlodipine on first day, 30th day and 60th day showed diastolic BP mean values as 96 ± 0.96 mmHg, 93 ± 1.63 mmHg and 88.6 ± 1.86 mmHg respectively with decrease of 4.2%. Patients treated with atenolol on first day, 30th day and 60th day showed diastolic BP mean values as 97.6 ± 1.53 mmHg, 91.8 ± 1.58 mmHg and 87.2 ± 1.78 mmHg respectively with decrease of 5.46%. Patients treated with captopril on first day, 30th day and 60th day showed diastolic BP mean values as 97.4 ± 1.05 mmHg, 91 ± 1.42 mmHg and 87.6 ± 1.94 mmHg respectively with decrease of 7.0%. Patients treated with Irbesartan on first day, 30th day and 60th day showed diastolic BP mean values as 97.2 ± 1.45 mmHg, 93.2 ± 1.44 mmHg and 85.6 ± 1.72 mmHg respectively with decrease of 11.30%. Results are shown in table No 02.

Table No 02: Changes in mean Diastolic BP from day 1st to day 60

Groups (n=75)	Day 1 st (mmHg)	Day 30 (mmHg)	Day 60 (mmHg)	Decrease % Day 0-60
Amlodipine	96 ± 0.96	93 ± 1.63	88.6 ± 1.86	4.20
Atenolol	97.6 ± 1.53	91.8 ± 1.58	87.2 ± 1.78	5.46
Captopril	97.4 ± 1.05	91 ± 1.42	87.6 ± 1.94	7.00
Irbesartan	97.2 ± 1.45	93.2 ± 1.44	85.6 ± 1.72	11.3

Mean±SEM: P<0.01 significantly decreases from 1st day

P<0.01 significantly decreases from day 1st and day 30

Ratio of side effects is described in table No 3 below.

Table No 03: Percentage of Side Effects with Four Antihypertensive Drugs

Side Effect	Captopril (%)	Irbesartan (%)	Amlodipine (%)	Atenolol (%)
Weight Loss	1	0	0	2
Dry Cough	30	5	0	0
Backache	0	1	0	0
Diarrhoea	0	0	0	0
Abdominal Pain	1	1	0	0
Weakness	0	1	1	1
Lethargy	3	2	4	6
Headache	4	32	1	8
Drowsiness	4	2	4	8

DISCUSSION:

While the treatment of hypertension there are many factors which play an affective role through different methods. Essential hypertension is a heterogeneous disease that is the reason its treatment is difficult but with such a wide verity of treatment methods, curing has become a little bit easy through medication and physical methods. DBP and SBP shown reduction through atenolol and amlodipine respectively as described in table one above. DBP and SBP reduced P value as <0.010 in captopril group and in Irbesartan group DBP and SBP also reduced P value as <0.010 . Warber et al in 1998 and 2010, made a comparison of atenolol with Irbesartan which is a long-acting antihypertensive receptor antagonist and found irbesartan more effective in decreasing DBP and SBP. Results of atenolol group of current study, as anti-hypertension are comparable with another study by Dahlofet et al carried out in 2002. Patients with moderate and mild essential hypertension, effectiveness and protection of amlodipine was less as compared to atenolol, reported by Freshman et al in 1988. Findings of this study are also same alike where atenolol compared to amlodipine, showed more effectiveness in the reduction of systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Observed maximum

reduction in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure with the use of irbesartan in our research study. Comparable results were observed in a study by Reves et al in 1998 which stated the irbesartan as most effective and safe anti-hypertension drug for the treatment of mild to moderate hypertension on the description of one dose per day. The results of present study were found also comparable with colleagues and pool study performed in 1998.

CONCLUSION:

According to the findings of our research study, the most effective and secure medicine for curing of hypertension is Irbesartan.

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